

USING THE CONCEPT OF MARKETING IN MANAGEMENT

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Abstract. *This article discusses integrated development of the concept of marketing at different levels of management in the field of tourism, analysis, planning, implementation and control over the implementation of measures to meet consumer demand and achieve certain goals in the field of tourism, the formation of an attractive image of the country and the region for tourists.*

Keywords: *tourism, concept of marketing, services, efficiency, market, region.*

INTRODUCTION. In the classical sense, marketing is defined as a system of actions for the mutual adaptation of goods, services and the market in order to achieve sustainable commercial success in the target market. Marketing provides contact between the producer and the consumer, helps to increase the efficiency of their exchanges. As a consequence, it is a goal-setting start of production, a means of minimizing the discrepancy between supply and demand. Marketing establishes and constantly supports not only commodity, but also information exchange between potential market participants.

The need for marketing, as a system, arises with the advent of competition in the market, when it becomes possible and necessary to build processes for the production and distribution of goods and services, starting from real demands and needs, and not to impose on consumers what is more profitable and easier to produce. The function of marketing is twofold: from providing knowledge of the market, on the one hand, to adapting and shaping the market, on the other.

The formation of the tourism services market, the need to develop the national tourism complex and the commercialization of tourism activities have led to the need to introduce marketing principles into the practice of tourism enterprises.

The logic of the development of market relations in the field of tourism determines the formulation and solution of such tasks as the study and segmentation of the tourism market, the qualitative and quantitative assessment of effective demand for tourism services, the positioning of tourism products, the use of communication tools and sales promotion.

In our opinion, the prerequisites for the effective development of marketing in tourism are the following conditions: free market relations, i.e. the ability to choose sales markets, business partners, set prices, conduct commercial work; free activity of the administration within the tourist enterprise to determine the goals of the company, strategies, management structures, distribution of funds according to budget items, etc.; saturation of the market with tourist services, the existence of a buyers' market; intense competition between tourism firms.

These conditions are typical for the tourism market as a whole. However, it should be noted that there are significant differences in the level of development of individual market segments. Today it is legitimate to talk about the saturation of the market with outbound tourism services - a wide offer of foreign tours.

Marketing is considered as a system containing certain components. Singling out and considering them in interrelation and interdependence, it is possible to determine the mechanism for implementing the concept of marketing in the field of tourism. Proceeding from this, the model

of the marketing system in the field of tourism proposed by us includes two main blocks: independent variables (reason) - the offer of a tourist product in certain market conditions; dependent variables (effect) - the perception of the proposed product by potential consumers of tourism services.

Research methodology. Systematic approach, abstract-logical thinking, grouping, comparison, factor analysis, selective observation methods were used in the research process.

Analysis and results. In the concept of marketing in the field of tourism, the main object of attention are the clients of the company with their needs and requirements. The firm organizes and coordinates its activities with the expectation of satisfaction of customer needs, profiting precisely from the creation and maintenance of customer satisfaction.

Analysis of the development of the concept of marketing in the field of tourism in our country and in foreign countries (USA, Germany, France, Russia, Italy, etc.) since the late 80s of the XX century. showed that it is fundamental to single out two fundamental aspects:

1. It is necessary to develop a comprehensive concept of marketing at different levels of management in the field of tourism: from the level of the country and regions to tourism enterprises and organizations;

2. The implementation of the concept of marketing in practice is impossible without marketing management, since it is the analysis, planning, implementation and control of activities to meet consumer demand and achieve certain goals in the field of tourism.

At the state level, this is the use of a marketing system in the formation and implementation of national and regional programs for the development of the tourism industry in the republic, region, the formation of an attractive image of the country and region for tourists.

At the level of a tourism enterprise, the concept of marketing must be consistently developed and affected by all aspects of activity, thereby solving a specific problem, i.e. how best to use available funds, how to make decisions with the least risk. Central task - adaptation of the company's strategy and tactics to the changing realities of the market. Development of a program for the development and support of the tourism industry, based on the analysis of the needs and demand for tourist services, requires a large amount of information about consumers and producers of tourist services, the activities of competitors, etc. This problem is solved by conducting a complex of marketing research. Their result is an analysis of the initial situation and specific recommendations for determining the prospects for activities in the tourism market.

The most important objects of the analysis of market opportunities in the field of tourism are: consumers (customers); tourism product; competitors; communications.

To develop marketing programs, segmentation is used using a combination of features: travel motivation, the degree of importance of tourism in the structure of consumer spending, the stereotype of tourist behavior, etc. Each of the market segments must correspond to a specific tourist offer.

Segmentation gives the characteristics that a tourist product should have in terms of the desires and preferences of consumers. For the formation of the national tourism product, important areas of analysis are indicated. The result of the analysis of the tourist product is the development of a strategy for its positioning in the market to attract a specific clientele and better meet the needs of a particular market segment.

An analysis of the main factors in the complex will allow a more reasonable approach to the development of a strategy of behavior in the market in order to achieve competitive advantages.

The following developments are the result of communication analysis: the state of awareness of potential customers about the tourist product; media preferences of various consumer segments; the effectiveness of promotional activities; assessment of the image of a tourist enterprise in the eyes of customers. The information obtained is necessary to develop a communication strategy and evaluate the response of target audiences to demand generation and promotion of tourism products.

The information obtained as a result of the conducted research allows us to determine the goals in the field of regional tourism development: to increase the reliability and profitability of the network of tourist transport parks; improve the equipment of tourist bases; increase the percentage of occupied places; more efficient use of the tourist production apparatus; to harmonize the development of tourism with the peculiarities of natural conditions; pursue a flexible pricing policy in different seasons; constantly adapt offers to changing tastes of tourists; encourage cooperation between organizations involved in tourism. When choosing a tourism development strategy, the National Tourist Complex (NTC), as well as tourism authorities, can focus not only on some of the listed goals, but also on their entire set, building an appropriate model for themselves.

An important component of the marketing concept is direct and feedback from consumers, which ensures the cyclical nature of the marketing process. Successful marketing relationships mean high quality service. A cycle of marketing communications has been developed, as well as a response from the clients of a travel company, where marketing communications and the level of service are reproduced in the process of providing tourist services. In the future, tactical decisions on the positioning of the tourist product are embodied in the creative concepts of advertising companies. We have developed an advertising company program, which can be the base for tourism enterprises. The program formulates the general goals and means of advertising influence. In a real situation, the goals are specified, the choice of advertising media is carried out taking into account the budget of the advertising company. In this regard, the task of its optimization is important. An iterative scheme for the optimal organization of an advertising company for a travel company is proposed.

When developing a placement plan in an advertising company, first of all, one should take into account the popularity and rating indicators of advertising media. Possible motives for advertising messages can be the following: the attractiveness of recreation on the proposed routes: natural conditions, quality of accommodation, food, service, staff qualifications, safety; attractive competitive prices; the opportunity to get the highest quality of service at the lowest price; the reliability of the company providing the trip: its experience, the seriousness of intentions, the reliability of its founders, the experience of previous trips - the absence of disruptions in them and the failure to fulfill the promise; it is possible to qualitatively highlight the priority (the main advertising argument) among the above motives with the help of a framework sociological study or, at least, a focus group.

The use of the concept of marketing in the formation and development of national tourism, the formation of the image of the country and regions that are attractive for tourism, is possible and necessary. However, the successful solution of the tasks set can only be achieved by combining the efforts of state and regional bodies responsible for shaping the image (including abroad) of tourism associations, enterprises and other organizations interested in the functioning of a civilized national tourism market in Uzbekistan.

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